

SOP

Guidance and Standard Operating Procedure

For SARS-CoV-2 Detection

**Department of Virology
BSMMU**

Chief Contributors

- **Dr. S M Rashed UI Islam**
Assistant Professor
Department of Virology
Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University (BSMMU)
- **Dr. Tahmina Akhter**
Assistant Professor
Department of Virology
Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University (BSMMU)
- **Dr. Sharmin Sultana**
Assistant Professor
Department of Virology
Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University (BSMMU)
- **Dr. Asish Kumar Ghosh**
Virologist
Narayanganj PCR Lab (attached)
300 bedded hospital
Khanpur, Narayanganj

Associate Contributors

- Dr. Md. Abdullah Omar Nasif, MD Resident, Department of Virology, BSMMU.
- Dr. Kaniz-E-Zannat, MD Resident, Department of Virology, BSMMU.
- Md. Shafayet Jamil, COVID-19 Laboratory, BSMMU.
- Avirup Saha, COVID-19 Laboratory, BSMMU.

NB: This guideline subjected to change and update frequently as per the situations. Any kind of notification for correction, modification or updates will be highly encouraged.

For Correspondence:

Dr. S M Rashed UI Islam (Assistant Professor), Department of Virology, BSMMU

Tel: +8801713236399; **email:** smrashed@bsmmu.edu.bd, smrashed1620@yahoo.com

Preface

Emerging infectious diseases, especially viral infections have appeared as a significant public health threat. In recent time, the Coronavirus disease-2019 (COVID-19) pandemic is the greatest challenge we have encountered since World War -II. COVID-19 is caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus-2 (SARS-CoV-2). At present, all countries are racing to slow the spread of the virus by testing and treating patients. The laboratories are playing a critical role in diagnosis and monitoring of viral disease as well as in the understanding of the genetic changes in the viral genome. Establishment of a reliable virology laboratory is a prerequisite for a strong public health response to emerging viral diseases. For good laboratory practice (GLP), there is an urgent need of guidance that are intended to provide the minimum requirements for establishing a COVID-19 laboratory and highlights the standard operating procedures (SOPs) for the sample collections, SARS-CoV-2 detection, biosafety precaution and waste management under resource constrains situations. Unfortunately, presently there is lack of such guidelines and SOPs. I am very happy to know that my colleagues have developed this SOP, which is intend to fill up this gap. I hope that, following this guidance and SOPs at all COVID-19 laboratories in Bangladesh, will help to identify COVID-19 cases efficiently and it would be a great help for physicians in patient management at all levels in the country.

Professor (Dr.) Saif Ullah Munshi

MBBS, MPhil, PhD

Chairman, Department of Virology, BSMMU

&

Head, COVID-19 Laboratory, BSMMU

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Introduction

As the coronavirus rushes across the globe, scientists are mobilizing in a united effort to confront, delay and stop its spread and subsequently save lives. In the absence of either proven effective therapy or a vaccine, diagnostic testing becomes a valuable tool. Although public health specialists implementing extreme measures to isolate the virus, most countries have been underprepared and as a result, they have faced community transmission before adequate testing was in place to allow for ample isolation and tracking. Therefore, number of laboratory for COVID-19 testing by Real-time PCR is increasingly throughout the country.

Backgrounds

Laboratory diagnosis plays a key role in identification and management of COVID-19 cases. Specimen collection, storage and transportation in a proper way are essential for correct diagnosis of the disease.

This SOP are prepared and followed by the COVID-19 laboratory established under the Department of Virology of Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University (BSMMU).

Purpose

This SOP are prepared and followed by the COVID-19 laboratory under the Department of Virology linked with triage based fever clinic at the Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University (BSMMU). The purpose of this document is to provide a guidance to all the laboratories and stakeholders involved in COVID-19 virus laboratory testing of patients throughout the country.

The SOP should be used by skilled laboratory personnel of all levels engaged in collection, transportation, laboratory detection and storage of specimen for SARS-CoV-2 RNA.

Source of Specimen

- Sample collection booth placed in fever clinic
- University hospital samples referred by physicians from the fever clinic.
- Other sources when comes through proper channel

Materials requirements for specimen collection

- a. Polyester fiber-tipped applicators Nylon/ Dacron/ Rayon swab
- b. Tongue depressors: disposable
- c. Sample storage reagent
- d. Sample release reagent or lysis buffer.
- e. Viral transport medium
- f. Sample particulars form

Personal protective equipment

- Gloves
- N95 mask or equivalent mask
- Gown and Cover all
- Eye protector/Face shield
- Head Cap
- Shoe cover

Antiseptic, disinfectants and disposal container

- Hand sterilizer: 70% Alcohol / Hexisol
- Biohazard Bag, sharp container
- Disinfectants: Na- hypochlorite solution (e.g. Clotech/ Clorex),/ Chlorine solution
- Biohazard bag (1'x2") to dispose of used PPE and other waste.

Other items

- Masking tape
- Scissors
- Zip lock bag
- Permanent marker
- Waste bin

Data collection forms/ lab. log book should contain following information: help in tracing patient's specimen and diagnosis

Patient's information:

- Unique identification (code) number
- Patient demographic information: age, sex, address with contact number, occupation
- Patient's clinical condition
- Diagnostic test results: local e.g. X-ray chest with findings of pneumonia

Specimen information requirements:

- Specimen name
- Specimen collection date and time
- Specimen collection location

Packaging & Transport

- Primary container e.g. cryo vial, eppendorf tube (should be air tight)
- Secondary container (Air tight Box/Bottle/Tube)
- Cool box/ vaccine carrier
- Ice packs (put ice packs in deep freezer before transport)
- A pen or permanent marker for labelling samples

Infrastructure, Instruments, equipment's and consumables required for COVID 19 Laboratory

Infrastructure:

- Sample collection booth
- COVID 19 Lab proper
 - ✓ Sample processing room
 - ✓ Amplification room
 - ✓ PPE doffing room
 - ✓ Lab garments, face shield, goggles etc. cleaning and drying room
 - ✓ Materials storage room
 - ✓ Report typing and online submission corners (Outer portion of Lab)
 - ✓ Laboratory members' rooms and fresh room facilities.

- ✓ Laboratory furniture should be sturdy. Open spaces between and under benches, cabinets and equipment should be accessible to cleaning.

Instrument and equipment

- Biosafety cabinets Class II-A2
- PCR work station
- -70 °C freezer
- -20 °C freezers
- 2-8°C freezers
- Table top centrifuge (24 well)
- Water bath
- Dry Heating block (24 wells)
- Vortex mixer
- Micropipettes (1000 µl)
- Micropipettes (200 µl)
- Micropipettes (20 µl)
- Micropipettes (10 µl)
- Autoclave – Two (one for decontamination and one for sterilization)
- Real time PCR instruments
- Distillation system
- Automated nucleic acid extractor
- Laboratory furniture (Lab tables, Lab chair, instrument desk, easily washable)
- Computer desk with computer, printer, internet connections

Consumables

- Personal Protective equipment's (N95 mask, Head cap, Eye shield/goggles, Face shield, shoe covers Boot/shoes, cover all)
- Gloves (Powder free)
- Gloves (Powdered)
- Absolute alcohol
- Hand sanitizer (70% alcohol based)
- Discard bags/Bio hazard bags
- Cleaning materials (Roll tissue)
- Filter tips 1000 ul

- Filter tips 200 ul
- Filter tips 20 ul
- Blue tips
- Yellow tips
- Eppendorf tube
- Sample storage box 96 box
- Falcon tube 50 ml
- Universal vial transport with sterile swab applicator (example BD)/Sample collection device

Reagents and supplies

- Diagnostic kits as per requirements of the laboratory or supplied by the authority
- Sample storage cry vials and boxes
- Sample processing rack
- Micropipette tips box
- PCR tubes (0.1 and 0.2 ml)
- PCR reagents (Taq polymerase, reverse transcriptase, primers, probes)
- RNA extraction kit
- -20°C cold block
- Other accessories.

Flow chart for SARS-CoV-2 testing at COVID-19 laboratory, BSMMU

**Standard Operating Procedures
for
SARS-CoV-2 Detection**

Purpose

This SOP are prepared and to be followed by the COVID-19 laboratory under the Department of Virology linked with triage based fever clinic at the Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University (BSMMU). The purpose of this document is to provide a guidance to all the laboratories and stakeholders involved in COVID-19 virus testing of patients throughout the country.

Aims

- Detection of COVID-19 (SARS-CoV-2) from Respiratory clinical specimens using Real-time PCR technique. This protocol uses the manufacturer's instruction to perform the tests.
- Name of the Kit used at the laboratory: Novel Coronavirus (2019-nCoV) Nucleic Acid Diagnostic Kit (PCR-Fluorescence Probing) Sansure Biotech Inc. (<http://eng.sansure.com.cn/>)

Essential Specimen/ Samples

- Naso-pharyngeal swab (NPS)
- Nasal swab (NS)
- Oro-pharyngeal swab (OPS)

Other preferred samples

- Bronchoalveolar lavage (BAL)
- Tracheal aspirate (TA)
- Sputum

Sample collection techniques

Precaution taken during collection of respiratory samples:

- Universal precaution with use of appropriate personal protective equipment (PPE).
- Properly-labelled, no spillage, packaged sample collection device was used.
- Clinical specimens were placed and transported to the laboratory promptly at 4°C.

Nasopharyngeal swabs

- Tilt patient's head back 70 degrees
- Insert swab into nostril (Swab should reach depth to distance from nostrils to outer opening of the ear)
- Leave swab in place in place for several seconds to absorb secretions
- Slowly remove swab while rotating it
- Place tip of swab into sample collection tube containing sample storage reagent and snap/cut off the applicator stick
- Insert to another nostril following the same procedures.

Steps to collect throat swab

- Ask the patient to sit on in front of specimen collector with neck flexion
- Depress the tongue with a tongue depressor
- Gently swab the posterior pharynx up and down several times.
- Break or cut the stick at the opening of vial; keep broken swab in the transport medium of the vial, and close and airtight the vial.

Instructions for collecting a throat swab

Steps for Tracheal aspirate collection

- Collect nasopharyngeal secretions by aspiration through a catheter connected to a mucus trap and fitted to a vacuum source. Tracheal aspirates were collected by a closed suction sample collection device
- Insert the catheter for 5-6 cm into the nostrils parallel to the palate. Apply the vacuum and withdraw the catheter slowly with a rotating motion.
- The secretion is aspirated into a sterile polypropylene collector tube
- 2-5 ml of tracheal aspirate is collected from each patient and normal saline wash is performed when respiratory secretion is very low.

Figure: Tracheal aspirate collection device

Figure: Tracheal aspirate collection

Sputum

Spontaneous expectoration/ induced sputum is the method of choice for collecting sputum samples. The sputum is then diluted 1:1 with an equal volume of PBS and it should be vortexed for 1 to 2 min to create a homogenized mixture of 2-5ml before RNA isolation process.

After collection of samples/specimens

- Specimens will be transported to the testing laboratory by dedicated vehicle.
- A small spill cleanup kit will be kept in the vehicle for immediate spill cleanup transport to the laboratory as soon as possible (within 48 hours if collected from outside)
- If needed keep the sample at + 2°C to + 8°C for a maximum period of two days
- Store at -20°C for short storage or -70°C for longer period;
- Avoid freeze-thaw cycle

Transport Precautions

- Adequate cushioning materials inside the box to absorb shocks during transport
- Adequate absorbing material to absorb any spillage should it occur
- Do not stick the request form on the specimen
- Specimen request forms should be put into a separate plastic bag
- The outer container, secondary containers and specimen racks for transport should be thoroughly cleansed and sprayed disinfectant in daily basis after work or when contaminated.

Labeling of Package (If sample collected from distant sources)

- Sender's, name, address and telephone number
- Whom to contact in case of emergency with telephone number
- Receiver's name, address and telephone number
- Proper shipping name
- Temperature storage requirements
- Quantity of dry ice inside the container
- Arrow mark to indicate upright direction

Responsibility of Sender

- Make advance arrangements with the carrier that the shipment will be accepted for appropriate transport
- Prepare necessary documentation, including permits, dispatch and shipping documents
- Notify the receiver in advance of transportation arrangements and expected date of delivery of shipment

Responsibility of Receiver

- Acknowledge receipt of specimen
- Verify the integrity of packaging
- Box to be opened by personnel wearing adequate PPE.
- Open within Biosafety cabinet
- Check the specimens with the data sent
- Inform about receiving the specimen

COVID-19 Lab

Introduction to the COVID-19 testing

The Novel Coronavirus (2019-nCoV) Nucleic Acid Diagnostic Kit (PCR-Fluorescence Probing) is a real-time RT-PCR test intended for the qualitative detection of nucleic acid from SARS-CoV-2 in nasopharyngeal swabs, oropharyngeal (throat) swabs, anterior nasal swabs, mid-turbinate swabs, nasal washes and nasal aspirates etc. from individuals who are suspected of COVID-19 by their healthcare provider. Results are indicated for the identification of SARS-CoV-2 RNA only the specimen tested. The SARS-CoV-2 RNA is generally detectable in respiratory specimens during the acute phase of infection. Positive results (Presence of SARS-CoV-2 RNA in tested specimen) should be made adjunct to the clinical correlation with patient history and other diagnostic information is necessary to determine patient infection status. Here to mention that, a positive result do not rule out bacterial infection or co-infection with other viruses or the agent detected may not be the definite cause of disease. In addition, a negative result do not preclude SARS-CoV-2 infection and should not be used as the sole basis for patient management decisions. Therefore, important to note that, negative results must be combined with clinical observations, patient history, and epidemiological information, rather it should be interpreted with cautions.

This Novel Coronavirus (2019-nCoV) Nucleic Acid Diagnostic Kit (PCR-Fluorescence Probing) is intended to be use by qualified, trained clinical laboratory personnel specifically instructed and trained in the techniques of real-time PCR and *in vitro* diagnostic procedures.

Kit principle

The Novel Coronavirus (2019-nCoV) Nucleic Acid Diagnostic Kit (PCR-Fluorescence Probing) is a real-time reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction (rRT-PCR) test. The 2019-nCoV primer and probe sets are designed to detect RNA from SARS-CoV-2 in respiratory specimens from patients who are suspected of COVID-19 by their healthcare provider. This kit is used for qualitative detection of the ORF1ab and N genes of SARS-CoV-2 RNA. By one simple step of centrifugation and lysis, the sample mixture can be directly added to the 2019-nCoV-PCR master mix (2019-nCoV-PCR Mix + 2019-nCoV-PCR-Enzyme Mix) to carry out rRT-PCR amplification.

Internal control targeting the RNase P gene monitor the sample collection, sample handling and rRT-PCR process to avoid false-negative results. The LoD of the kit is 200 copies/mL.

Components Included within the Kit

Serial no	Reagent & accessories	Main ingredients
1	Sample Release Reagent	Lysis buffer
2	2019-nCoV-PCR Mix	Primers, Probes, dNTPs, MgCl ₂ , Rnasin, PCR buffer
3	2019-nCoV-PCR-Enzyme Mix	RT Enzyme, Taq Enzyme
4	2019-nCoV-PCR-Positive Control	In vitro transcriptional RNA for ORF1ab, N gene and internal control RNase P gene
5	2019-nCoV-PCR-Negative Control	Saline
6	Sample Storage Reagent	0.9% saline, Rnasin
7	Swab stick	Collection stick with synthetic tip, such as nylon or Dacron®, and an aluminum or plastic shaft.

Figure: Components of the PCR kits

Notes on the controls Materials

- 2019-nCoV-PCR-Negative Control: A “no template” (negative) control is used to monitor whether there is contamination for the rRT-PCR process and is used in each detection run.
- 2019-nCoV-PCR-Positive Control: A positive template control is used to monitor whether the rRT-PCR process works properly and is used in each detection run.
- An internal control for RNase P gene is used to monitor the sample collection, handling and rRT-PCR process and is used in each sample amplification.

Laboratory Procedure

Testing algorithm in short:

Specimen processing protocol for Nasopharyngeal & Throat Swab

- 1. Throat swab or Nasopharyngeal swab stored in Sample storage buffer tube**

⇓

- 2. Mix thoroughly by vortexing for 5-10 seconds**

⇓

- 3. Place the samples on Heat block at 56°C in for 30 mins/ 65°C in for 10 mins to inactivate**

⇓

- 4. Take out each component-- PCR mix, Enzyme mix, Positive control (PC), Negative control (NC) & Lysis buffer to thaw at room temperature (20°C-25°C). Centrifuge all the components at 2,000 RPM for 10-15 seconds.**

⇓

- 5. According to quantity of Specimen, PC & NC prepare Master Mix in a tube -- (26µl PCR mix + 4µl Enzyme Mix)/Test**

⇓

- 6. Mix thoroughly by Vortexing & Centrifuge @ 2000 RPM for 10-15 seconds**

⇓

Continue

⇓

7. Take PCR tube according to the quantity of Specimen, PC & NC.

⇓

8. Add **10 µl Lysis buffer** in each tube (Check all tube afterwards)

⇓

9. Add **10 µl of Heat Inactivated sample** in each tube & **mix fully** by pipetting **3-5** times (Check all tube, afterwards)

⇓

10. Stand for **10 mins in Room Temperature** for lysis

⇓

11. Add **30 µl Master Mix** to each tube & mix thoroughly by pipetting

⇓

12. Centrifuge @ **2000 RPM** for **10-15 seconds** and then

13. **Set the instrument and start the process.**

Sputum sample processing (Not collected in Sample storage tube)

1. Inactivate the sputum sample @ 56°C for 30 mins/ 65°C for 10 mins in a dry Heat block.

3. Take out each component-- **PCR mix, Enzyme mix, Positive control (PC), Negative control (NC) & Lysis buffer** to thaw at room temperature (20°C-25°C) or hold them in hands for fully thawing until no ice crystal in each tube). **Centrifuge** all the components at **2,000 RPM** for **10-15 seconds**.

4. According to quantity of **Specimen, PC & NC** prepare **Master Mix** in a tube --
(26µl PCR mix + 4µl Enzyme Mix)/Test

5. Mix thoroughly by **Vortex & Centrifuge @ 2000 RPM for 10-15 s**

6. Take PCR tube according to the quantity of Specimen, PC & NC.

7. Add **10 µl Lysis buffer** in each tube

8. Add **10 µl of Heat Inactivated sample** in each tube & **mix fully** by pipetting **3-5** times

9. Stand for **10 mins in Room Temperature** for lysis

10. Add **30 µl Master Mix** to each tube & mix thoroughly by pipetting

11. Centrifuge @ **2000 RPM** for **10-15 seconds** and then

12. **Set the instrument and start the process.**

Sample extraction (Buffer-based extraction method)

Specimen collected in Sample Storage Reagent supplied kit, sample processing steps follows the Sample Release Reagent RNA fast-releasing technology provided in the kit (One tube method). In brief, 10 µl Lysis buffer are given in each pcr tube followed by 10 µl of Heat Inactivated sample in each tube & mix fully by pipetting for 3-5 times. This mixture is allowed to stand for 10 minutes in room temperature for lysis. After 10 minutes incubation, 30 µl Master Mix are added each tube & mix thoroughly by pipetting in the same manner. For master mix preparation, please see the following section.

Master mix preparation procedure

- Take out each component from the diagnostic kit and place them at room temperature. Allow the reagents to equilibrate at room temperature, then vortex each of the tube. Then, centrifuge all the components at 2,000rpm for 10-15 seconds in case of solution on the lids and tube walls.
- According to the quantity of test specimens, negative control and positive control, pipette appropriate quantity components in proportion (26 uL 2019-nCoV-PCR Mix /test+ 4uL 2019-nCoV-PCR-enzyme mix/test), and fully mix them into PCR-Master mix. Centrifuge them instantaneously ((2,000rpm for 10-15 seconds)) for add to specimen-lysis buffer mix in PCR tube. This centrifuge step is important to avoid solution trapped in the tube's wall/cap. The remaining reagent after use must be stored at -20°C immediately for later use.
- 30 µL of 2019-nCoV-PCR Master Mix are added into each PCR tube containing samples and cap the tube immediately. In addition, 2019-nCoV-PCR-Negative Control and 2019-nCoV-PCR-Positive Control are also prepared in the same fashion. The mixture is centrifuged at 2000 rpm for 10 seconds, and placed into real-time PCR instrument and the exact location of controls and each specimen are linked with COVID 19 detection program.

Amplification procedure (This protocol may vary according to Real time instrument)

- Start Real time PCR system and turn on the computer connected to the system first, then turn on (open/click) the PCR system software.
- Load the instrument: Open the tray door, load the prepared plate containing samples and controls into the plate holder in the instrument. Be ensure that, the plate is properly aligned in the holder. Close the tray door.
- Next, set up the experiment run:
- Select PCR test detector channel:
 - Select FAM channel (ORF-lab region) and ROX (N gene) to detect the nucleic acid of 2019-nCoV virus;
 - Select CY5 channel to test internal control.
 - Select Quencher Dye to none.

Recommend thermal cycle parameter setting and initiate the test:

	Steps	Temperature	Time	Cycle no.
1	Reverse Transcription	50 °C	30 minutes	1
2	cDNA pre-denaturation	95 °C	1 minute	1
3	Denaturation	95 °C	15 seconds	45
	Annealing, extension and fluorescence collection*	60 °C	30 seconds *	
4	Instrument cooling	25 °C	10 seconds	1

*Data collection

Result analysis

Results will be saved automatically when reactions are completed. Analyze amplification curve of *target of detection* and internal control. Adjust Start, End and Threshold values of Baseline of the graph according to analysis result. Adjust the values according to the actual test run. Start value can be set between 3-15, and End value between 5-20. Adjust the amplification curve of negative control to be flat or below threshold. Change the amplification plot to linear mode and put the threshold line above the flat line/noise. Click “Analyze” to implement the analysis window to record results.

All test controls should be examined prior to interpretation of patient results. If the controls are not valid, the patient results cannot be interpreted. The Ct cutoff value of this kit is set as 40, the end user is required to review each, and every fluorescent curves before final interpretation. All the positive curves should be typical S-shape amplification curves or without plateau for weakly positive samples.

Quality Control

The positive control and negative control for each run are interpreted as described in Table. The test result is treated as valid if all the conditions in the above-mentioned are met for the same test.

	2019-nCoV-PCR-Negative Control	2019-nCoV-PCR-Positive Control
Ct value	No Ct or Ct > 40 at channel FAM, ROX and CY5 (internal control)	≤ 35 at channel FAM, ROX and CY5 (internal control)

Reference Range

Through the research on reference values, the Ct reference value of target gene is determined to be 40, the Ct reference value of internal control is determined to be 40.

Explanation of detection result

Conclusion	Amplification curve characteristics
2019-nCoV Positive	There is typical S-shape amplification curve detected at FAM and/or ROX channel, and the amplification curve which is detected at CY5 channel, Ct≤40.
2019-nCoV Negative	There is no typical S-shape amplification curve (No Ct) or Ct> 40 detected at FAM and ROX channel, and the amplification curve, which is detected at CY5 channel, Ct ≤ 40.

Note: There is no typical S-shape amplification curve detected at FAM, ROX and CY5 channel (No Ct), or Ct > 40. It is indicated that the specimen's concentration is too low, or there are interfering substances that inhibit the reaction. The test result is invalid. An investigation should be performed to find out and exclude the reasons; collection of a specimen may require and retest the specimens. Experienced and trained personnel should analyze this amplification curve and decision are made accordingly.

Figure: IC curve

Figure: ORF1ab curve

Figure: N gene Curve

Figure: Positive controls curve (ORF1ab, N gene and IC)

Figure: Negative control curve. Set the threshold level just above the line.

Figure: Non-specific curve.

Figure: Non-specific amplification curve

Limit of detection (LoD):

LoD studies are used to determine the lowest detectable concentration of SARS-CoV-2 RNA at which approximately 95% of all (true positive) replicates test positive. The manufacturer's validation studies found that, the limit of detection of this kit is 200 copies/mL.

Reporting the results:

All the Laboratories are required to report all results to the appropriate authority and/or MIS, DGHS control room/DHIS2 for combined circulation to generate national COVID 19 cases status.

Limitations

- Poor specimen quality, improper sample collection, improper transportation, improper laboratory processing, or a limitation of the testing technology can cause false positive and false negative results.
- Mutation in the target sequence of SARS-CoV-2 or change in the sequence due to virus evolution may lead to false negative results.
- Improper reagent storage may lead to false negative results.
- Use of this assay is limited to personnel who are trained in the procedure. Failure to follow these instructions may result in erroneous results.
- Test results of the diagnostic kit can only be used as an aid in clinical diagnosis. Symptoms and physical signs, disease history, other laboratory examinations and therapeutic reactions of the patients should be comprehensively considered for the clinical diagnosis and treatment.
- Unverified interfering substances or PCR inhibitors may lead to false negative or invalid results.
- Cross-contamination occurring in the specimen processing may lead to false positive results.
- The fast-releasing technology using Sample Releasing Reagent has been evaluated only for use in combination with the Sample Storage Reagent provided in the Novel Coronavirus (2019-nCoV) Nucleic Acid Diagnostic Kit. Sample Release Reagent used with specimens stored in other storage, preservation, or transport media (VTM/UTM) not provided in the kit has not been fully validated and may cause false negative results.

FAQ

What is the Novel Coronavirus (2019-nCoV) Nucleic Acid Diagnostic Kit (PCR-Fluorescence Probing)?

The test is designed to detect the virus that causes COVID-19 in respiratory specimens, for example nasal, nasopharyngeal or oral swab etc.

What does it mean if I have a positive test result?

If you have a positive test result, it is very likely that you have COVID-19. Therefore, it is also likely that you may be placed in isolation to avoid spreading the virus to others. There is a very small chance that this test can give a false positive result. In every cases, laboratory test results should always be considered in the context of clinical observations and epidemiological data in making a final diagnosis and patient management decisions. Patient management should follow national guidelines based on medical history and symptoms.

What does it mean if I have a negative test result?

A negative test result for this test means that SARS-CoV-2 RNA was not present in the specimen above the limit of detection. However, a negative result does not rule out COVID-19 and should not be used as the sole basis for treatment or patient management decisions. For COVID-19, a negative test result for a sample collected while a person has symptoms usually means that COVID-19 did not cause your recent illness.

It is possible for this test to give a false negative result in some people with COVID-19. This means that you could possibly still have COVID-19 even though the test is negative. If this is the case, your healthcare provider will consider the test result together with all other aspects of your medical history (such as symptoms, possible exposures, and geographical location of places you have recently traveled) in deciding how to care for you. It is important to work with healthcare provider to help you understand the next steps you should take.

Biosafety during specimen collection and handling for COVID-19

- Treat all clinical samples as potentially infectious
- Follow standard precautions of hand hygiene and PPE use
- Wash hand with soap-water/ use 70% alcohol/ other hand sterilizer before and after work
- Decontaminate used gloves with 70% ethanol/ soap water before put off, and put off PPEs, keep in biohazard bag/ designated container
- Decontaminate by 5% sodium hypochlorite for 10 mins /by autoclave used PPEs
- Decontaminate work place and biosafety cabinet with 5% sodium hypochlorite/ethanol for 5-10 minutes daily two times (before and after procedures)
- Avoid formation of aerosols and droplets
- Avoid recapping needles
- Be careful about spillage of specimen If spill occurs
- Apply bleach/ 5% sodium hypochlorite/ Ethanol/ detergent on spill
- Wait for 5-10 mins
- Remove decontaminated spill carefully
- Swab the area with soap-water/ bleach /chlorine solution
- Allow to dry the place
- Report immediately if developed cough, fever or any respiratory symptoms

Biosafety at COVID 19 Laboratory

- Do not eat, drink, smoke, apply cosmetics or handle contact lenses in areas where reagents and human specimens are handled.
- Handle all specimens as if infectious using safe laboratory procedures. Refer to Interim Laboratory Biosafety Guidelines for Handling and Processing Specimens Associated with 2019-nCoV <https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-nCoV/lab-biosafety-guidelines.html>.
- Dispose of hazardous or biologically contaminated materials according to the practices of BSMMU.
- The package insert are to be read carefully prior to operation. The Novel Coronavirus (2019-nCoV) Nucleic Acid Diagnostic Kit (PCR-Fluorescence Probing) is only for emergency use with a prescription, as an *in vitro* diagnostic (IVD) test. Each step of operation, from specimen collection, storage and transportation, and laboratory testing, should be strictly conducted in line with relevant biosafety regulations and molecular laboratory management.

- Separate laboratory areas, dedicated to performing predefined procedures of the assay, are required. a) 1st Area: Preparation Area—Prepare testing reagent: b) 2nd Area: specimen processing—Process the specimen and controls: c) 3rd: Amplification Area—PCR conducted
- All pipette tips and centrifuge tubes in the assay should be sterile and DNase/RNase-free. To prevent contamination, filtered pipette tips are required and should be replaced after the addition of each reagent or sample.
- Dispose of waste in compliance BSMMU regulations.
- All lab workbench and supplies should be cleaned and disinfected regularly using 70% Ethanol or 10% bleach.

Equipment sterilization/decontamination procedure

Environmental surface decontamination:

Environmental cleaning or decontamination is to reduce the number of infectious agents that may be present on (frequently touched) surfaces and minimize the risk of transfer of microorganisms from one person/object to another, thereby reducing the risk of cross-infection. Infectious agents can survive in the environment and on surfaces for many hours or even days. Decontamination removes pathogens from contaminated surfaces and items.

Two key principles of environmental hygiene are-

Step 1 – Cleaning:

- Clean BEFORE disinfection
- Clean with moping /washing with water-detergent

Step 2 – Disinfection

Disinfect items and surfaces that are:

- In contact with a patient's secretion, touch or mucosa
- Frequently touched by healthcare workers – Soap, detergent,
- 0.5-1% sodium hypochlorite solution, (Chlotech, chlorox)
- Bleaching solution (Mixture of 1 lit water + two table spoon full bleaching powder)
- 70% ethanol
- Lyzol
- Phenolic compound (e.g. Finis)
- 2% Gluteraldehyde (Cidex),
- Formaldehyde fumigation etc

Linen

- Use clean or sterile cloths (as appropriate).
- Change linen everyday
- Place soiled or used linen or cloths into a bag
- Decontaminate all cloths/dresses used by patients and health care workers by autoclave or washing with soap-water.

Waste Management

- Keep waste in biohazard bag/waste bag in wastes bins
- Close/secure waste bag when two third to be filled up
- Decontaminate waste by autoclave or chemical (1% sodium hypochlorite) ;
- Incineration (ideal), if not available, do burning
- Burning waste in Pits (>8 feet deep) in premises, behind the hospital building.

Note: Use 1% Sodium Hypochlorite or Soap water or 70% Ethanol or UV as appropriate for decontamination of equipment, surface, table, beds, floors, toilets

- Prepare disinfectants in recommended dilutions
- Decontaminate all horizontal surfaces in patient care areas twice a day
- Decontaminate surfaces, tables, equipment in after discharge and before admission/arrive
- Decontaminate surface of examination table/other equipment in direct contact with patients between patients
- Dampen cleaning cloths before use—never use dry dusting or sweeping.

Preparation of 1% Sodium hypochlorite Solution from 5.25% chlotek / Chlorox

- 1% Sodium hypochlorite Solution
10 ml of 5% Solution is to be diluted in 1L of water
- From powder form:
1 L water + two table spoon of Bleach

Disposal of waste

Treat any waste possibly contaminated SARS COV-2 virus as clinical waste according to the healthcare facility preferably by autoclaving or incineration. For waste disposal the following guidelines have to be followed.

- All wastes should be disposed of in suitable containers or biohazard bags
- All wastes should be treated as clinical (infectious) waste
- Staff responsible for removing waste should wear PPE
- Not to contaminate the outside of the bag
- To use two bags if outside is contaminated (double bagging).
- Close the bag and prepare for disposal to the testing laboratory.
- Autoclaving is the preferred method before disposal of waste
- Waste disposal bags should have appropriate biohazard labelling
- Bags be treated and disposed of as per the policy of authority (BSMMU)
- To follow national regulations pertaining to hospital waste.

Serial no	Type of waste	Example	Color of waste bin/container
1	General waste	Leftover meals, administrative rubbish, and paper, sweeping	Black
2	Clinical/Lab waste without sharp objects	Materials used in lab/patients care	Yellow
3	Clinical waste with sharp objects	Needles or scalpel blades, knives, broken glass materials etc.	Red
4	Recyclable waste	Saline kits	Green
5	Liquid waste	Vomiting, blood and blood products	Blue

Table: Color-coded bin for waste management

Precautions to take after completing the clean-up and decontamination

- Wash hands with soap and water immediately after removing PPE, cleaning/ disinfection work.
- Discard all used PPE in a double-bagged biohazard bag, securely sealed and labeled. After sealing the bio-hazard bag, wear another pair of gloves and spray hypochlorite solution around the bio-hazard bag. Remove and discard the gloves in the yellow color/or designated bin.
- The staff should be aware of symptoms, and should report to their occupational health service if they develop symptoms.

The **CORRECT** way to tie the bag

Always wear gloves

Bag shouldn't be more than 1/2 full

Twist the top

Tie a knot

Liquid Spill Management

- Decontaminate spills of potentially infectious materials.
- Wear PPE and protective gloves.
- Using a pair of forceps and gloves, carefully retrieve broken glass and sharps if any, and use a large amount of folded absorbent paper to collect small glass splinters. Place the broken items into the puncture proof sharps container.
- Cover spills of infected or potentially infected material on the floor with paper towel/ blotting paper/newspaper.
- Pour freshly prepared 1% Sodium hypochlorite solution and leaves for 20-30 minutes for contact.
- Place all soiled absorbent material and contaminated swabs into a designated waste container. Then clean the area with gauze or mop with water and detergent with gloved hands.

Appendixes

COVID-19 Laboratory

Appendix 1: Protection level of Health care worker in COVID-19 management

কোভিড-১৯ সেবাদানকারীদের পিপিই ব্যবহারের আদর্শ নিয়মাবলী

 সার্জিক্যাল মাস্ক
 সার্জিক্যাল ক্যাপ

 ডিসপোজেবল গ্লাভস
 কর্মস্থলের পোশাক

প্রয়োজনবোধে ডিসপোজেবল আইসোলেশন পোশাক ব্যবহার করা যেতে পারে

 ধাপ-১

- ট্রায়াজ/সন্দেহভাজন রোগী বাছাই এলাকা
- সাধারণ বহির্বিভাগ (শ্বাসতন্ত্রের উপসর্গ ব্যতিত)
- প্রবেশ পথ- বন্দর এলাকা (কোভিড-১৯ স্ক্রিনিং কাজে নিয়োজিত)
- সন্দেহভাজন/ নিশ্চিত কোভিড-১৯ রোগী বহনকারী অ্যানুলেপ ড্রাইভার/হেলপার

 N95 মাস্ক/FFP2
 সুরক্ষাকারী চশমা

 ডিসপোজেবল গ্লাভস
 সার্জিক্যাল ক্যাপ

ব্যক্তিগত সুরক্ষা সামগ্রী (PPE Coverall)

 ধাপ-২

- জ্বর, কাঁশি এবং ফু কণার এর সাথে সম্পর্কিত বহির্বিভাগ।
- আইসোলেশন/ICU ওয়ার্ড (পরিচ্ছন্নতাকর্মী, সেবা দানকারী)
- সরাসরি কোভিড-১৯ রোগীকে তার বাড়িতে সেবাদানকারী স্বাস্থ্যসেবা কর্মী।
- সন্দেহভাজন/নিশ্চিতভাবে সংক্রমিত ব্যক্তির নমুনা সংগ্রহের সময়
- কোভিড-১৯ রেডিওলজি বিভাগের টেকনিশিয়ান
- কোভিড-১৯ সংক্রমিত ব্যক্তির পরীক্ষায় ব্যবহৃত যন্ত্রপাতি পরিষ্কার করার সময়।
- কোভিড-১৯ রোগী স্থানান্তরে নিয়োজিত ব্যক্তি।
- কোভিড-১৯ রোগীর সাথে সাক্ষাতকালে।
- কোভিড-১৯ মৃদু সংক্রমণের কারণে হোম কোয়ারেন্টাইনে থাকা ব্যক্তির স্বাস্থ্য-সেবা দানকারী।

 N95 মাস্ক/Respirator
 সুরক্ষাকারী চশমা এবং ফেসশিল্ড

 ডিসপোজেবল গ্লাভস
 সার্জিক্যাল ক্যাপ

ব্যক্তিগত সুরক্ষা সামগ্রী (PPE Coverall)

 ধাপ-৩

- সন্দেহভাজন অথবা নিশ্চিতভাবে সংক্রমিত ব্যক্তির ট্র্যাকিংস্টেমী, ট্র্যাকিং ইনটিউবেশন, ব্রেকফাইব্রোকোপি, গ্যাস্ট্রোএন্টারোলজীকাল পরীক্ষা, এডোকোপি/AGP (Aerosol Generating Procedure) ইত্যাদি প্রক্রিয়া সম্পন্নকালে।
- সন্দেহভাজন অথবা নিশ্চিতভাবে সংক্রমিত ব্যক্তির ময়নাতদন্তকারী
- কোভিড-১৯ রোগীর NAAT (Nucleic Acid Amplification Test) পরীক্ষাকালে।
- সংস্কার/দাফন কাজে নিয়োজিত ব্যক্তি যদি মৃতদেহের সংস্পর্শে আসেন।

সাধারণ রোগের চিকিৎসার ক্ষেত্রে সার্জিক্যাল মাস্ক, হ্যান্ড স্যানিটাইজার এবং সামাজিক দূরত্ব (>১মিটার) আবশ্যিক

বিশেষ দৃষ্টব্য:

১. বায়োসেফা কেন্দ্রে কর্মরত সকল কর্মকর্তা কর্মচারী অবশ্যই সার্জিক্যাল মাস্ক ব্যবহার করবেন।
২. লেভেল-১ নিরাপত্তা নিশ্চিত করার জন্য জরুরী বিভাগ, সংক্রামক রোগ বহির্বিভাগ, শ্বাসতন্ত্র বিষয়ক বহির্বিভাগ, স্ট্রাকচারাল বা এডোকপি পরীক্ষা কক্ষ বিভাগে (হেম- গ্যাস্ট্রোইন্টেস্টাইনাল এডোকপি, ব্রেকফাইব্রোকপি, ল্যারিস্কোপি ইত্যাদি) কর্মরত সবাই অবশ্যই সার্জিক্যাল মাস্কের পরিবর্তে N95 (FFP-2) মাস্কের ব্যবহার নিশ্চিত করবেন।
৩. সন্দেহভাজন/নিশ্চিত কোভিড-১৯ রোগীর শ্বাসতন্ত্রের নমুনা সংগ্রহ করার সময় লেভেল-২ নিরাপত্তা নিশ্চিত করার জন্য নমুনা সংগ্রহকারী অবশ্যই তার নিজের মুখে নিরাপত্তা বেট্টা পরিধান করবেন।

Appendix 2: Hand washing technique

How to Handwash?

WASH HANDS WHEN VISIBLY SOILED! OTHERWISE, USE HANDRUB

 Duration of the entire procedure: 40-60 seconds

0 Wet hands with water;

1 Apply enough soap to cover all hand surfaces;

2 Rub hands palm to palm;

3 Right palm over left dorsum with interlaced fingers and vice versa;

4 Palm to palm with fingers interlaced;

5 Backs of fingers to opposing palms with fingers interlocked;

6 Rotational rubbing of left thumb clasped in right palm and vice versa;

7 Rotational rubbing, backwards and forwards with clasped fingers of right hand in left palm and vice versa;

8 Rinse hands with water;

9 Dry hands thoroughly with a single use towel;

10 Use towel to turn off faucet;

11 Your hands are now safe.

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May 2020

Appendix 3: Steps for hand rubbing with alcohol based formulation

How to Handrub?

RUB HANDS FOR HAND HYGIENE! WASH HANDS WHEN VISIBLY SOILED

 Duration of the entire procedure: 20-30 seconds

1a Apply a palmful of the product in a cupped hand, covering all surfaces;

2 Rub hands palm to palm;

3 Right palm over left dorsum with interlaced fingers and vice versa;

4 Palm to palm with fingers interlaced;

5 Backs of fingers to opposing palms with fingers interlocked;

6 Rotational rubbing of left thumb clasped in right palm and vice versa;

7 Rotational rubbing, backwards and forwards with clasped fingers of right hand in left palm and vice versa;

8 Once dry, your hands are safe.

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May 2009

Appendix 4: Donning of gloves

Appendix 5: Doffing of gloves

Appendix 6: Correct use of face mask

Facemask Do's and Don'ts

For Healthcare Personnel

When putting on a facemask

Clean your hands and put on your facemask so it fully covers your mouth and nose.

DO secure the elastic bands around your ears.

DO secure the ties at the middle of your head and the base of your head.

When wearing a facemask, don't do the following:

DON'T wear your facemask under your nose or mouth.

DON'T allow a strap to hang down. DON'T cross the straps.

DON'T touch or adjust your facemask without cleaning your hands before and after.

DON'T wear your facemask on your head.

DON'T wear your facemask around your neck.

DON'T wear your facemask around your arm.

When removing a facemask

Clean your hands and remove your facemask touching only the straps or ties.

DO leave the patient care area, then clean your hands with alcohol-based hand sanitizer or soap and water.

DO remove your facemask touching ONLY the straps or ties, throw it away*, and clean your hands again.

*If implementing limited-reuse: Facemasks should be carefully folded so that the outer surface is held inward and against itself to reduce contact with the outer surface during storage. Folded facemasks can be stored between uses in a clean, sealable paper bag or breathable container.

Additional information is available about how to safely put on and remove personal protective equipment, including facemasks:

<https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/hcp/using-ppe.html>.

[cdc.gov/coronavirus](https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus)

Appendix 7: Correct use of Respirator

Respirator On / Respirator Off

When you put on a disposable respirator

Position your respirator correctly and check the seal to protect yourself from COVID-19.

Cup the respirator in your hand. Hold the respirator under your chin with the nose piece up. The top strap (on single or double strap respirators) goes over and rests at the top back of your head. The bottom strap is positioned around the neck and below the ears.

Place your fingertips from both hands at the top of the metal nose clip (if present). Slide fingertips down both sides of the metal strip to mold the nose area to the shape of your nose.

Place both hands over the respirator, take a quick breath in to check the seal. Breathe out. If you feel a leak when breathing in or breathing out, there is not a proper seal.

Select other PPE items that do not interfere with the fit or performance of your respirator.

Do not use a respirator that appears damaged or deformed, no longer forms an effective seal to the face, becomes wet or visibly dirty, or if breathing becomes difficult.

Do not allow facial hair, jewelry, glasses, clothing, or anything else to prevent proper placement or to come between your face and the respirator.

Do not crisscross the straps.

Do not wear a respirator that does not have a proper seal. If air leaks in or out, ask for help or try a different size or model.

Do not touch the front of the respirator during or after use! It may be contaminated.

When you take off a disposable respirator

Remove by pulling the bottom strap over back of head, followed by the top strap, without touching the respirator.

Discard in a waste container.

Clean your hands with alcohol-based hand sanitizer or soap and water.

Employers must comply with the OSHA Respiratory Protection Standard, 29 CFR 1910.134, which includes medical evaluations, training, and fit testing.

Additional information is available about how to safely put on and remove personal protective equipment, including respirators:
<https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/hcp/using-ppe.html>

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cdc.gov/coronavirus

Appendix 8: Donning of PPE

SEQUENCE FOR PUTTING ON PERSONAL PROTECTIVE EQUIPMENT (PPE)

The type of PPE used will vary based on the level of precautions required, such as standard and contact, droplet or airborne infection isolation precautions. The procedure for putting on and removing PPE should be tailored to the specific type of PPE.

1. GOWN

- Fully cover torso from neck to knees, arms to end of wrists, and wrap around the back
- Fasten in back of neck and waist

2. MASK OR RESPIRATOR

- Secure ties or elastic bands at middle of head and neck
- Fit flexible band to nose bridge
- Fit snug to face and below chin
- Fit-check respirator

3. GOGGLES OR FACE SHIELD

- Place over face and eyes and adjust to fit

4. GLOVES

- Extend to cover wrist of isolation gown

USE SAFE WORK PRACTICES TO PROTECT YOURSELF AND LIMIT THE SPREAD OF CONTAMINATION

- Keep hands away from face
- Limit surfaces touched
- Change gloves when torn or heavily contaminated
- Perform hand hygiene

PPE পরার সময় কি কি জিনিস তৈরি থাকতে হবে

- ✓ গাইডলাইনস এর নিয়ম অনুযায়ী PPE সকল সামগ্রী
- ✓ একটি ধোয়ার উপযোগী জামা-কাপড় [যেমন OT তে ব্যবহার হয় এমন জামা-কাপড়]
- ✓ একজোড়া প্লাস্টিকের কভার সহ জুতা যা ধোয়ার উপযোগী
- ✓ কব্জির অংশে গ্লাভস ও গাউন এর মাঝখান এবং মাস্ক এর চারপাশ সীল করার জন্য ২ ইঞ্চি মাস্কিং টেপ
- ✓ কাঁচি

বিশেষ দৃষ্টি আকর্ষণ:

গাইডলাইনস অনুযায়ী এবং দৈনন্দিন কাজের অভিজ্ঞতা থেকে তৈরি করা হয়েছে, যা অন্যান্য ল্যাবরেটরি এর জন্য প্রযোজ্য না ও হতে পারে

Appendix 9: Doffing of PPE

**HOW TO SAFELY REMOVE PERSONAL PROTECTIVE EQUIPMENT (PPE)
EXAMPLE 1**

There are a variety of ways to safely remove PPE without contaminating your clothing, skin, or mucous membranes with potentially infectious materials. Here is one example. **Remove all PPE before exiting the patient room except a respirator, if worn. Remove the respirator after leaving the patient room and closing the door.** Remove PPE in the following sequence:

1. GLOVES

- Outside of gloves are contaminated!
- If your hands get contaminated during glove removal, immediately wash your hands or use an alcohol-based hand sanitizer
- Using a gloved hand, grasp the palm area of the other gloved hand and peel off first glove
- Hold removed glove in gloved hand
- Slide fingers of ungloved hand under remaining glove at wrist and peel off second glove over first glove
- Discard gloves in a waste container

2. GOGGLES OR FACE SHIELD

- Outside of goggles or face shield are contaminated!
- If your hands get contaminated during goggle or face shield removal, immediately wash your hands or use an alcohol-based hand sanitizer
- Remove goggles or face shield from the back by lifting head band or ear pieces
- If the item is reusable, place in designated receptacle for reprocessing. Otherwise, discard in a waste container

3. GOWN

- Gown front and sleeves are contaminated!
- If your hands get contaminated during gown removal, immediately wash your hands or use an alcohol-based hand sanitizer
- Unfasten gown ties, taking care that sleeves don't contact your body when reaching for ties
- Pull gown away from neck and shoulders, touching inside of gown only
- Turn gown inside out
- Fold or roll into a bundle and discard in a waste container

4. MASK OR RESPIRATOR

- Front of mask/respirator is contaminated — **DO NOT TOUCH!**
- If your hands get contaminated during mask/respirator removal, immediately wash your hands or use an alcohol-based hand sanitizer
- Grasp bottom ties or elastics of the mask/respirator, then the ones at the top, and remove without touching the front
- Discard in a waste container

5. WASH HANDS OR USE AN ALCOHOL-BASED HAND SANITIZER IMMEDIATELY AFTER REMOVING ALL PPE

PERFORM HAND HYGIENE BETWEEN STEPS IF HANDS BECOME CONTAMINATED AND IMMEDIATELY AFTER REMOVING ALL PPE

PPE খোলার সময় কি কি জিনিস তৈরি থাকতে হবে

- ✓ একটি খালি কক্ষ যেখানে পানির সংযোগ সহ একটি বেসিন থাকবে
- ✓ PPE খোলার সময় ফ্যান এবং এ সি সাময়িক ভাবে বন্ধ রাখতে হবে
- ✓ একটি বর্জ্য ফেলার পাত্র বা ওয়েস্ট বিন
- ✓ Biohazard ব্যাগ [১টি বড় ও ১টি ছোট]
- ✓ দুই জোড়া Hand Gloves
- ✓ Hand Sanitizer অথবা সাবান পানির মিশ্রণ যুক্ত স্প্রে বোতল
- ✓ গাইডলাইনস এর নিয়ম অনুযায়ী ধাপে ধাপে PPE খুলতে হবে
- ✓ N95 Mask পরা অবস্থায় বড়ো বায়ো হাজার্ড ব্যাগ টি টাইট করে বন্ধ করতে হবে
- ✓ N95 Mask পরা অবস্থায় কক্ষের ভিতর 1% Sodium Hypochlorite Solution স্প্রে করতে হবে [Doffing এর স্থান ও বর্জ্য ফেলার পাত্রের চারপাশে]
- ✓ 1% Sodium Hypochlorite Solution স্প্রে করার কিছুক্ষণ পর N95 Mask টি খুলে ছোট বায়ো হাজার্ড ব্যাগ এ রেখে সীল করতে হবে (ডিসকার্ড অথবা পুনরায় ব্যবহারের জন্য) এবং দ্রুত Surgical Mask পরে Biohazard ব্যাগ এর মুখ সঠিক ভাবে বন্ধ করে নির্দিষ্ট স্থানে ফেলে দিয়ে কক্ষ থেকে বেরিয়ে যেতে হবে
- ✓ ব্যবহৃত ফেস শিল্ড টি 1% Sodium Hypochlorite মিশ্রণ এ ভিজিয়ে বেসিনে সাবান পানি দিয়ে ধুয়ে পুনরায় ব্যবহারের জন্য সংরক্ষণ করতে হবে
- ✓ ব্যবহৃত গাউন এবং প্লাস্টিকের জুতা টি সাবান মিশ্রিত পানি দিয়ে ৩০ মিনিট ভিজিয়ে রেখে ধুয়ে ফেলতে হবে (ধোয়ার ব্যবস্থা না থাকলে সীল করা যায়, এমন আর একটি ব্যাগ এ নিয়ে বাড়ি গিয়ে নিয়ম অনুযায়ী ধুয়ে ফেলতে হবে)
- ✓ করোনা প্রতিরোধ করার জন্য উপরের প্রতিটি ধাপ অতি গুরুত্ব পূর্ণ, বিধায় সতর্কতার সাথে পালন করতে হবে
- ✓ এ ক্ষেত্রে একজন সাহায্যকারী সাথে থাকা উত্তম

বিশেষ দৃষ্টি আকর্ষণ:

গাইডলাইনস অনুযায়ী এবং দৈনন্দিন কাজের অভিজ্ঞতা থেকে তৈরি করা হয়েছে, যা অন্যান্য ল্যাবরেটরি এর জন্য প্রযোজ্য না ও হতে পারে

Appendix 10: Preparation of disinfectants (City corporation guidelines)

ঢাকা উত্তর সিটি কর্পোরেশন

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শেখ হাসিনার মূলনীতি
গ্রাম শহরের উন্নতি

করোনা ভাইরাস প্রতিরোধে ঘরে বসে সহজেই জীবাণুনাশক তৈরি করুন

করোনা ভাইরাস প্রতিরোধে ব্লিচিং পাউডার ব্যবহার করে ঘরে বসে সহজেই জীবাণুনাশক তৈরি করা যায়।

ব্লিচিং পাউডার বাজারে স্বল্পমূল্যে কিনতে পাওয়া যায়। ব্লিচিং পাউডার দিয়ে দুই ধরনের তরল জীবাণুনাশক তৈরি করা যায়। একটি বেশি ঘনত্বের (১ : ১০ ঘনত্বের) তরল জীবাণুনাশক, যা দ্বারা অধিক সংক্রামক বর্জ্য, হাসপাতালের বর্জ্য ইত্যাদি জীবাণুমুক্ত করা হয়। আরেকটি কম ঘনত্বের (১ : ১০০ ঘনত্বের) তরল জীবাণুনাশক যা সাধারণ পরিষ্কারের কাজ যেমন আসবাবপত্র, যন্ত্রাংশ, ফ্লোর, গাড়ি ইত্যাদি জীবাণুমুক্ত করতে ব্যবহৃত হয়।

অধিক সংক্রামক বর্জ্য, হাসপাতালের বর্জ্য ইত্যাদি জীবাণুমুক্ত করতে বেশি ঘনত্বের (১:১০ ঘনত্বের) তরল জীবাণুনাশক তৈরির নিয়মঃ ২ লিটার পানিতে ১ টেবিল চামচ ব্লিচিং পাউডার গুলিয়ে ঢাকনা দিয়ে ৩০ মিনিট রেখে দিন। তারপর নিচে জমা হওয়া তলানি ফেলে দিয়ে উপরের স্বচ্ছ তরল জীবাণুনাশক হিসাবে ব্যবহার করুন।

২ লিটার পানি

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১ টেবিল চামচ ব্লিচিং পাউডার

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২ লিটার জীবাণুনাশক

সাধারণ পরিষ্কারের কাজ যেমন আসবাবপত্র, যন্ত্রাংশ, ফ্লোর, গাড়ি ইত্যাদি জীবাণুমুক্ত করতে কম ঘনত্বের (১ : ১০০ ঘনত্বের) তরল জীবাণুনাশক তৈরির নিয়মঃ ২০ লিটার পানিতে ১ টেবিল চামচ ব্লিচিং পাউডার গুলিয়ে ঢাকনা দিয়ে ৩০ মিনিট রেখে দিন। তারপর নিচে জমা হওয়া তলানি ফেলে দিয়ে উপরের স্বচ্ছ তরল জীবাণুনাশক হিসাবে ব্যবহার করুন।

২০ লিটার পানি

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১ টেবিল চামচ ব্লিচিং পাউডার

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২০ লিটার জীবাণুনাশক

**Appendix 11: Specimen collection and storage conditions (Adapted from WHO
COVID-19 laboratory guideline)**

Specimen type	Collection materials	Storage temperature until testing in-country laboratory	Recommended temperature for shipment according to expected shipment time
Nasopharyngeal and oropharyngeal swab	Dacron or polyester flocced swabs*	2-8 °C	2-8 °C if ≤ 5 days -70 °C (dry ice) if > 5 days
Bronchoalveolar lavage	Sterile container *	2-8 °C	2-8 °C if ≤ 2 days -70 °C (dry ice) if > 2 days
(Endo)tracheal aspirate, nasopharyngeal or nasal wash/aspirate	Sterile container *	2-8 °C	2-8 °C if ≤ 2 days -70 °C (dry ice) if > 2 days
Sputum	Sterile container	2-8 °C	2-8 °C if ≤ 2 days -70 °C (dry ice) if > 2 days
Tissue from biopsy or autopsy including from lung	Sterile container with saline or VTM	2-8 °C	2-8 °C if ≤ 24 hours -70 °C (dry ice) if > 24 hours
Serum	Serum separator tubes (adults: collect 3-5 ml whole blood)	2-8 °C	2-8 °C if ≤ 5 days -70 °C (dry ice) if > 5 days
Whole blood	Collection tube	2-8 °C	2-8 °C if ≤ 5 days -70 °C (dry ice) if > 5 days
Stool	Stool container	2-8 °C	2-8 °C if ≤ 5 days -70 °C (dry ice) if > 5 days
Urine	Urine collection container	2-8 °C	2-8 °C if ≤ 5 days -70 °C (dry ice) if > 5 days

* For transport of samples for viral detection, use viral transport medium (VTM) containing antifungal and antibiotic supplements. Avoid repeated freezing and thawing of specimens. If VTM is not available sterile saline may be used in place of VTM (in such case, duration of sample storage at 2-8 °C may be different from what is indicated above).

Appendix 12: Wrong placement of mask after use. For reuse, use sealable bag

Appendix 13: Wrong doffing and discards of PPE after use. Use separate bag/person for each PPE junk

Appendix 14: Improper submersion of linen for decontamination under detergent mixed water. Rinse properly to decontaminate the inner reusable lab gown and accessories

Appendix 15: Wrong mixing of hazardous waste with general waste and overflowing waste bag.

Appendix 16: Step wise manpower with their responsibilities

Steps	Designation	Laboratory placement	Responsibilities
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Laboratory Technologists Laboratory attendants 	Sample collection booth	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sample collection and labelling as per patients information Sample transport to laboratory
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Junior Virologist MD resident Scientific officer Laboratory technologist 	Sample processing room	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Receive samples as per ID/labelling Sample processing RNA isolation and processing for real time PCR Sample storage as per results Instrument and equipment decontamination and maintenance Reagents, consumables and non-consumables stock managements
3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Junior Virologists MD residents Scientific officer Laboratory technologist 	Amplification room	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Receive processed samples for amplification Real time instrument set up as per samples ID and number Results analysis and report generation Result submission for report generation
4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Computer operator Data entry Laboratory technologist 	Report generation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Patients particulars entry and record keeping Report/result entry Submission to authorized body for circulation
4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Laboratory Manager Scientific officer Laboratory technologist 	Whole laboratory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Laboratory protective equipment's set up, Biosafety and waste managements & decontamination process and monitoring as a whole Laboratory accessories supports and maintenance
5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Senior Virologists 	Whole laboratory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Supervision all the members working according to placement Co-ordination among the laboratory members Stock and requirements submission
6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Head 	Whole laboratory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chief of the laboratory Overall responsibility for activities of the laboratory Administrative and logistics supports Reporting results to authorized body

Further readings and information

- Laboratory biosafety manual. Third edition. Available from:
https://www.who.int/csr/resources/publications/biosafety/WHO_CDS_CSR_LYO_2004_11/en/
- 2019-NOVEL CORONAVIRUS (COVID-19) SPECIMEN COLLECTION KIT INSTRUCTIONS. Available from:
<https://health.ri.gov/publications/instructions/COVID-19-Specimen-Collection-Kit.pdf?fbclid=IwAR0rJv2dlaxClpEtMvjOzchXzEEeNSIS-3nfbB7DFetN1IKsawUhNkaEUVEs>
- CDC 2019-Novel Coronavirus (2019-nCoV) Real-Time RT-PCR Diagnostic Panel. Available from: <https://www.fda.gov/media/134922/download>
- National Guideline for Health Care Provider On Infection Prevention and Control of COVID 19 pandemic in Healthcare Setting. Available from:
https://dghs.gov.bd/images/docs/Guideline/IPC%20Module%20for%20COVID-19%20for%20frontline%20HCW_20.3.2020.pdf
- Laboratory biosafety guidance related to the novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV). Available from: <https://www.who.int/docs/default-source/coronaviruse/laboratory-biosafety-novel-coronavirus-version-1-1.pdf>
- Proper Use and Care of the Biosafety Cabinet. Available from:
https://www.uab.edu/ehs/images/docs/ss/ss_biosafetycabinet.pdf
- PREPARATION OF VIRAL TRANSPORT MEDIUM. Available from:
<https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/downloads/Viral-Transport-Medium.pdf>
- Laboratory testing for coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) in suspected human cases. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/10665-331501>
- DGHS guidelines. Available from:
<https://dghs.gov.bd/index.php/bd/publication/guideline>
- CDC. Information for Laboratories about Coronavirus (COVID-19). Available from:
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- CDC. Interim U.S. Guidance for Risk Assessment and Work Restrictions for Healthcare Personnel with Potential Exposure to COVID-19. Available from:
<https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/hcp/guidance-risk-assesment-hcp.html>